

Protocol for a cross-sectional study on companion pigs and hobby pigs in Denmark

Helene Ane Jensen^{1,*}, Anette Ella Boklund¹, Abbey Olsen¹, Thomas Bøker Lund², Peter Sandøe^{1,2}, Søren Saxmose Nielsen¹

¹Department of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, University of Copenhagen

²Department of Food and Resource Economics, University of Copenhagen

* Corresponding author. E-mail address: helene.jensen@sund.ku.dk (H.A. Jensen)

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1 Background and purpose

From 2017 to 2022, the number of pigs kept as companion animals in Denmark increased by 67% (from 922 to 1,541) according to the Danish Central Husbandry Register (CHR, 2024). However, we have little knowledge of the motivation for owners to keep companion pigs or hobby pigs, under which conditions they are held, and the degree of biosecurity in these holdings. According to the EU legislation, all kept pigs are considered production animals, even if kept as a companion or hobby animals. This means that several requirements for keeping the pigs exist; for example, all pig holdings in Denmark must be registered in the CHR (Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Fisheries of Denmark, 2024). Furthermore, from the municipalities, there are legal restrictions on where pigs may be kept in the country. We have reason to believe that some holdings of companion pigs and hobby pigs are not registered in the CHR, but we do not have any information about the proportion or their location. Moreover, we lack information about the owners' motivations to keep pigs on a companion animal or hobby level.

In 2023, the majority (96%) of the African swine fever (ASF) outbreaks in domestic pigs in Europe was reported in pig holdings with less than 100 pigs (EFSA, 2024). With a pig population of 11 million pigs (Statistics Denmark, 2024), an outbreak of ASF in Denmark would have major economic consequences for the Danish pig production (Halasa et al., 2016). To identify relevant risk pathways for potential introduction of ASF virus into small pig holdings and potential transmission to larger, commercial holdings, it is necessary to investigate the conditions under which companion and hobby pigs are kept, their surroundings, contact with other animals and people, feeding, identification, origin, breeding, slaughter, and disposal of pigs and their waste.

Based on the above, we would like to elucidate the following through a questionnaire survey (Appendix A):

- 1) The number of companion pig and hobby pig holdings in Denmark
- 2) The location of these holdings (at postal code level)
- 3) The conditions under which companion and hobby pigs are kept, including their surroundings, direct and indirect contact with other animals and people, feeding, identification, origin, breeding, slaughter, and disposal of pigs and their waste
- 4) The motivation of owners to keep companion and hobby pigs
- 5) The owners' attachment to their companion and hobby pigs

Our plan is to publish the results of the study in one or more reports, peer-reviewed scientific articles, and popular scientific contributions. The findings will subsequently form the basis of a risk assessment of the probability of introduction of ASF virus in companion and hobby pig holdings, and of the probability of transmission of ASF virus from a holding with companion and hobby pigs to a commercial holding with more than 100 pigs. The purpose of the risk assessment is to reduce the probability of the introduction of the ASF virus into Danish pig holdings by providing decision-makers with information on potential risk pathways. In addition, some of the findings will contribute to a better understanding of how pigs are kept on a companion and hobby level.

2 Populations

2.1 Study unit

The CHR includes categories for holdings with companion pigs and hobby pigs, respectively: A companion pig holding is defined as "a pig holding in which the animal or the animals are kept as companion animals, comparable to a dog, and where there is no intention of slaughtering the

animal(s)", while a hobby pig holding is "a pig holding where the primary purpose of keeping the animals is not economic gain, or where income from the holding contributes only marginally to the owner's total earnings" (correspondence with the Danish Veterinary and Food Administration, August 2024). In the above Objectives 1-3, the study unit is the individual holding with companion pigs or hobby pigs, while the study unit in Objectives 4-5 is the owner of the holding.

2.2 Target population

The target populations are holdings with companion pigs and hobby pigs in Denmark (Objectives 1-3) and their owners (Objectives 4-5).

2.3 Source population

The source population is holdings with companion pigs and hobby pigs in Denmark that are registered in the CHR and/or whose owners are members of pig groups on Facebook. The owners are required to currently have or have had companion pigs or hobby pigs in the study period (described in Section 4.3 on inclusion criteria).

2.4 Study population

The study population is holdings with companion pigs and hobby pigs from the source population with owners who agree to participate in the study.

3 Study design

The cross-sectional study is conducted as a questionnaire survey aimed at owners of companion pigs and hobby pigs. The questionnaire consists of a combination of open and closed (categorised) questions. The findings of the study may form the basis for future hypothesis-based studies.

4 Participation in the study: Recruitment and inclusion criteria

We will recruit owners of companion pigs and hobby pigs via CHR (data extraction from 1 April 2025) and Facebook. To reduce the risk of overlap between owners recruited via the two data collection paths, we state at the beginning of the questionnaire that we only wish one response per household. In addition, we state that the questionnaire was distributed through various routes, and that the respondent should not fill in the questionnaire again if they have already responded to the questionnaire based on another invitation. To be able to differentiate between the respondents recruited via CHR and via Facebook, we ask the owners how they found the questionnaire. We will collect data in 2025 starting in August.

4.1 Recruitment of owners in CHR

We have retrieved a list from the CHR of all holdings registered as a companion pig holding or a hobby pig holding. As of 11 April 2025, 510 companion pig holdings and 912 hobby pig holdings were registered in the CHR. Our aim is to collect responses from 100 owners from a randomly generated list of all holdings of companion and hobby pigs in the CHR. The list of holdings is in random order, and we contact owners starting from the top of the list. If we are unable to reach an owner, we move on to the next one on the list, aiming to include responses from 100 CHR-registered owners in the sample.

We will contact the owners via e-mail or telephone after obtaining their contact information, for example via Krak. If the owner agrees to participate, they will either be interviewed by telephone by Helene Ane Jensen or fill out the questionnaire themselves via a link sent to their e-mail. The sample

size of 100 is based on a sample size calculation aimed at estimating a proportion (e.g. prevalence). We calculated the sample size to be 97, assuming an estimated proportion (p) of 0.5, an allowable error (L) of 0.1, and an alpha of 0.05.

4.2 Recruitment of owners on Facebook

We share a post about the study, including a link to the questionnaire, in Facebook groups for owners of companion pigs and hobby pigs. In addition, we create an advertisement on Facebook targeting owners of companion pigs and hobby pigs. We will collect data for one month, after which the questionnaire link is deactivated. Halfway through the data collection period, the post is reshared. Moreover, the post is made shareable to enable Facebook users to share the post with their contacts (snowball sampling).

4.3 Inclusion criteria

To be eligible for inclusion in the study, the owner must have or have had companion pigs and/or hobby pigs in Denmark in the study period from 1 January 2022 to 1 May 2025. All types of companion and hobby pigs are included in the study. The terms “companion pig holdings” and “hobby pig holdings” are defined in Section 2.1 on the study unit and contain less than 100 pigs. Holdings with 100 or more pigs are excluded. We include partial responses of the questionnaire and will indicate how many responses are partial when reporting the results. Owners without a permanent address in Denmark are also included. It will be voluntary for the owners to provide us with the postal code of the address where the pigs are held. Owners who do not wish to provide the postal code are included in the total number of responses but are excluded from the analyses of the location data.

5 Data management and analysis

Data are collected in a questionnaire in SurveyXact (Rambøll Management Consulting, Aarhus). Once the data collection is completed, we will import the data as an Excel file (Microsoft, Redmond, WA, USA). The results of the questionnaire survey will be reported in a descriptive analysis, where the responses to each question are described and summarised in proportions and frequencies for companion holdings and hobby holdings, respectively.

6 Validity, bias and uncertainty

6.1 External validity: Selection bias

Part of the source population is registered in the CHR, while another part consists of owners who are members of companion and hobby pig groups on Facebook. There may be companion and hobby pig holdings that are not registered in the CHR. By recruiting via social media, we can therefore reach both registered and unregistered holdings. However, using social media for recruitment may introduce self-selection bias if owners who are members of companion and hobby pig groups on Facebook differ from those who are not members of such groups.

6.2 Internal validity: Information bias

We reduce the risk of recall bias by limiting the study period to approximately 3 years, not extending further back than 2022. There can be a risk of response bias (prestige bias or social desirability bias), since the questions related to compliance with national legislation may be sensitive, for example the registration of the holding in the CHR. We try to reduce this risk by assuring the participants that all data will be published in pseudonymized form, once the data analysis is complete (for more

information, please refer to Section 8 on ethical considerations). Moreover, we try to reduce the risk of misclassification bias by sending the questionnaire for review to relevant stakeholders and experts (representatives from the Danish Veterinary and Food Administration, Danish Agriculture & Food Council Landbrug, SEGES Innovation, University of Copenhagen) before the data collection begins. Additionally, there may be a risk of misclassification in the categorisation of the holding when owners register it in the CHR. We try to reduce this risk by asking the owners about the number of pigs in their holding. Holdings with 100 or more pigs are excluded from the study.

6.3 Selective reporting

We will report the responses to all questions in the questionnaire to avoid selective reporting. We include partial responses, which may affect the representativeness of the study.

6.4 Other biases or uncertainties

The Danish Veterinary and Food Administration periodically conducts campaigns providing information about the legislation on keeping companion and hobby pigs. This may lead current owners to be more aware of the legislation than former owners, who have ceased keeping companion and hobby pigs. Conversely, former owners may have stopped keeping pigs because they became aware of the legislation.

7 Interviews and pilot testing of the questionnaire

We will test the content and relevance of the questionnaire by conducting interviews with owners and having owners pilot test the questionnaire before the data collection begins. Helene Ane Jensen will conduct the interviews of 4-5 owners, following an interview guide with the themes: motivation for keeping pigs, under which conditions the pigs are kept, and biosecurity. Interviewees are recruited on Facebook.

8 Ethical considerations

The processing of personal data was approved by The Faculty of Health and Medical Sciences (reference ID 514-1172/25-3000) at the University of Copenhagen, and The Research Ethics Committee for Faculty of Health and Medical Sciences found the study compliant with relevant Danish and International standards and guidelines for research ethics (case no. 504-0608/25-5000).

Data will be published in pseudonymous format. The name, phone number and e-mail of the owner is deleted once the owner has been contacted and either agreed or declined to participate. The information is not linked to their response to the questionnaire. The respondents are informed that they can send an e-mail to Helene Ane Jensen to be informed about the study results after the completion of the study. It is voluntary for the respondents to provide the postal code of the address where pigs are kept. This information will be used to map the locations of holdings with companion pigs and hobby pigs in Denmark. Information about the postal code will be pseudonymized, and in all publications, the information will be aggregated to a level where individual owners and holdings cannot be identified. For this, we will use the guidelines of Statistics Denmark.

Data will be kept by Helene Ane Jensen on a secured H-drive at UCPH servers. The pseudonymous data are shared within the project group. We plan to publish the results in one or more scientific articles.

Authorship follows the "Vancouver rules" (ICMJE, n.d.). The project is co-funded by the Danish Veterinary Consortium (DK-VET).

9 Project management

The project is a part of the PhD project of Helene Ane Jensen at the Section for Animal Health and Welfare, Department of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, University of Copenhagen. The project group consists of Associate Professor Anette Boklund, Professor Søren Saxmose Nielsen, Assistant Professor Abbey Olsen, Professor Peter Sandøe, Associate Professor Thomas Bøker Lund and PhD student Helene Ane Jensen. Søren Saxmose Nielsen is responsible for the project.

10 References

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- Statistics Denmark (Danmarks Statistik), 2024. Data from the StatBank Denmark: The pig population by quarter and by type, total number of pigs in the third quarter of 2024. [www.statistikbanken.dk/SVIN den 9. august 2024](http://www.statistikbanken.dk/SVIN%20den%209.%20august%202024).
- The Central Husbandry Register (CHR), 2024. <https://chr.fvst.dk/chri/faces/frontpage>.

Appendix A: Questionnaire

Information about the holding

In this questionnaire, we define "companion pigs" and "hobby pigs" in the following ways:

Companion pigs are pigs that are kept as companion animals, comparable to a dog, and where there is no intention of slaughtering the animal(s).

Hobby pigs are pigs that are held on a hobby level, for example for slaughter or land cultivation, but where the primary purpose of keeping the animals is not economic gain, or where income from the holding contributes only marginally to the owner's total earnings.

Please note that we only wish one response per household. This questionnaire was distributed through various routes, if you already filled it out based on another invitation, please do not fill it again. Please answer the questions with the option(s) that you think is most appropriate.

#	Questions	Options
1	How did you find this questionnaire?	<input type="checkbox"/> Via Facebook <input type="checkbox"/> I was contacted via telephone or e-mail <input type="checkbox"/> An acquaintance shared the questionnaire with me <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify)
2	Do you currently have or have you had one or more hobby pigs in the period 2022-2025? This applies both if you own/owned pigs privately or have/had the main responsibility for caring for pigs in an institution (e.g. small-scale petting farm for kids, or kindergarten). Please select all options that apply.	<input type="checkbox"/> I currently have one or more hobby pigs <input type="checkbox"/> I had hobby pigs in the period 2022-2025, but no longer have them <input type="checkbox"/> No (the questionnaire is closed if the answer is no to both questions 2 and 3)
3	Do you currently have or have you had one or more companion pigs in the period 2022-2025? This applies both if you own/owned pigs privately or have/had the main responsibility for caring for pigs in an institution (e.g. small-scale petting farm for kids, or kindergarten). Please select all options that apply.	<input type="checkbox"/> I currently have one or more companion pigs <input type="checkbox"/> I had companion pigs in the period 2022-2025, but no longer have them <input type="checkbox"/> No (the questionnaire is closed if the answer is no to both questions 2 and 3)
4	Are/were the pig(s) kept privately or in an institution (e.g. small-scale petting farm for kids, or kindergarten)? Multiple answers can be selected.	<input type="checkbox"/> In a private household <input type="checkbox"/> In an institution (e.g. kindergarten, school, playground) <input type="checkbox"/> On a farm with other livestock <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify)
5	If the owner keeps/kept hobby pigs: How many hobby pigs do/did you have on average on a given day during the period 2022 to 2025? Please write your answer in numbers.	[Numerical answer]
6	If the owner keeps/kept companion pigs:	[Numerical answer]

	How many companion pigs do/did you have on average on a given day during the period 2022 to 2025? Please write your answer in numbers.	
7	What breed(s) do/did you have/had? Multiple answers can be selected.	<input type="checkbox"/> Pot-bellied pig <input type="checkbox"/> Kunekune <input type="checkbox"/> Meishan <input type="checkbox"/> Mangalitsa/mangalica <input type="checkbox"/> Mini- or miniature pig (crossbreed) <input type="checkbox"/> Other breed (please specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Do not know
8	What other animal species have been at the address at the same time as the pig(s)? Multiple answers can be selected.	<input type="checkbox"/> No other animal species <input type="checkbox"/> Dog <input type="checkbox"/> Cat <input type="checkbox"/> Rabbit <input type="checkbox"/> Rodent (e.g. guinea pig, hamster, chinchilla, mouse, rat) <input type="checkbox"/> Poultry or other captive birds <input type="checkbox"/> Horse <input type="checkbox"/> Cattle <input type="checkbox"/> Sheep <input type="checkbox"/> Goat <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify)
9	Do/did the companion/hobby pigs have access to the food or water of other animals (e.g. dog bowl)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
10	Can/could the companion/hobby pigs come into contact with the other animal species on the premises?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No

Information about the owner, motivation to keep the pig and attachment to the pig

The following questions are about you, your motivation to keep pigs and attachment to them.

11	Please enter your year of birth	[Numerical answer]
12	Please indicate your gender	<input type="checkbox"/> Male <input type="checkbox"/> Female <input type="checkbox"/> None of the above <input type="checkbox"/> Prefer not to answer
13	What is your highest completed level of education?	<input type="checkbox"/> Elementary school / primary school <input type="checkbox"/> High school <input type="checkbox"/> Vocational school <input type="checkbox"/> Short-cycle higher education <input type="checkbox"/> Medium-cycle higher education (bachelor's level) <input type="checkbox"/> Long-cycle higher education (master's level) or PhD <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify)

14	If the owner has pigs in a private household or on a farm with other livestock: Which type of home do you live in?	<input type="checkbox"/> House (e.g. terraced house, detached house/villa) <input type="checkbox"/> Apartment <input type="checkbox"/> Farm <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify)
15	If the owner has pigs in a private household or on a farm with other livestock: Do you live alone (excluding animals)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
A	If the owner has pigs in a private household or on a farm with other livestock and does not live alone: Who do you live with (excluding animals)? Multiple answers can be selected.	<input type="checkbox"/> One person over the age of 17 <input type="checkbox"/> Several people over the age of 17 <input type="checkbox"/> One child aged 0-17 years <input type="checkbox"/> Several children aged 0-17 years
16	If the owner keeps/kept hobby pigs: For what purposes were the hobby pig(s) acquired? Multiple answers can be selected.	<input type="checkbox"/> As a companion animal <input type="checkbox"/> For meat production <input type="checkbox"/> For land cultivation <input type="checkbox"/> For educational/teaching purposes <input type="checkbox"/> For breeding and sale/rehoming <input type="checkbox"/> To participate in competitions, exhibitions, shows, or other gatherings <input type="checkbox"/> For truffle hunting <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Do not know
17	If the owner keeps/kept companion pigs: For what purposes were the companion pig(s) acquired? Multiple answers can be selected.	<input type="checkbox"/> As a companion animal <input type="checkbox"/> For meat production <input type="checkbox"/> For land cultivation <input type="checkbox"/> For educational/teaching purposes <input type="checkbox"/> For breeding and sale/rehoming <input type="checkbox"/> To participate in competitions, exhibitions, shows, or other gatherings <input type="checkbox"/> For truffle hunting <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Do not know
18	The following questions are only for owners of companion pigs (not for owners of hobby pigs)	
A	If the owner has pigs in a private household or on a farm with other livestock: Who was the companion pig acquired for? If you have more than one companion pig, please answer with reference to your favourite pig. Multiple answers can be selected.	<input type="checkbox"/> Myself <input type="checkbox"/> Another person over the age of 17 <input type="checkbox"/> A child aged 0-17 years <input type="checkbox"/> As companionship for other animals (e.g. another pig)

B	Who is responsible for taking care of the companion pig? If you have more than one companion pig, please answer with reference to your favourite pig. Multiple answers can be selected.	<input type="checkbox"/> Myself <input type="checkbox"/> Another person over the age of 17 <input type="checkbox"/> A child aged 0-17 years
C	If the owner has pigs in a private household or on a farm with other livestock: Who in the household do you think is most attached to the companion pig? If you have more than one companion pig, please answer with reference to your favourite pig.	<input type="checkbox"/> Myself <input type="checkbox"/> Another person over the age of 17 <input type="checkbox"/> A child aged 0-17 years
	In the following questions, we ask you to think about the pig or pigs to which you feel most attached. How much do you agree with the following statements?	0=strongly disagree, 1=somewhat disagree, 2=somewhat agree, 3=strongly agree
D	My pig knows when I'm feeling bad	
E	My pig and I have a very close relationship	
F	I play with my pig quite often	
G	I consider my pig to be a friend	
H	My pig means more to me than any of my friends	
I	I love my pig because it never judges me	
J	Pigs deserve as much respect as humans do	
K	I feel that my pig is a part of my family	
	The following questions are only for owners of both companion pigs and dogs	
	You have previously indicated that you have dogs. In the following questions, we ask you to think about the dog or dogs to which you feel most attached. How much do you agree with the following statements?	0=strongly disagree, 1=somewhat disagree, 2=somewhat agree, 3=strongly agree
L	My dog knows when I'm feeling bad	
M	My dog and I have a very close relationship	
N	I play with my dog quite often	
O	I consider my dog to be a friend	
P	My dog means more to me than any of my friends	
Q	I love my dog because it never judges me	
R	Dogs deserve as much respect as humans do	
S	I feel that my dog is a part of my family	
	The following questions are only for owners of both companion pigs and cats	
	You have previously indicated that you have cats. In the following questions, we ask you to think about the cat or cats to which you feel most attached. How much do you agree with the following statements?	0=strongly disagree, 1=somewhat disagree, 2=somewhat agree, 3=strongly agree
T	My cat knows when I'm feeling bad	
U	My cat and I have a very close relationship	
V	I play with my cat quite often	
W	I consider my cat to be a friend	
X	My cat means more to me than any of my friends	
Y	I love my cat because it never judges me	
Z	Cats deserve as much respect as humans do	
AA	I feel that my cat is a part of my family	

Identification, origin and breeding

19	Is/was the holding of companion/hobby pigs registered in the Central Husbandry Register (CHR)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Not as far as I know
20	What is/was the postal code of the area where the pigs are/were kept? Answering this question is optional. We use this information to get an idea of where in Denmark most companion/hobby holdings are. Please write your answer in numbers.	[Numerical answer]
21	Please indicate the distance (in km) from the address where the companion/hobby pigs are/were kept to the nearest public road (give your best estimate). Please write your answer in numbers.	[Numerical answer]
22	Please indicate the distance (in km) from the address where the companion/hobby pigs are/were kept to the nearest forest of at least ½ hectare (=5,000 m ²) with trees ¹ (give your best estimate). Please write your answer in numbers.	[Numerical answer]
23	Please indicate the distance (in km) from the address where the companion/hobby pigs are/were kept to the nearest commercial pig holding (give your best estimate). Please write your answer in numbers.	<input type="checkbox"/> [Numerical answer] <input type="checkbox"/> Do not know
24	Please indicate the distance (in km) from the address where the companion/hobby pigs are/were kept to the nearest nature conservation area where wild boars have been released (give your best estimate). Please write your answer in numbers.	<input type="checkbox"/> [Numerical answer] <input type="checkbox"/> Do not know
25	Where was/were the companion/hobby pig(s) acquired or purchased from? Multiple answers can be selected.	<input type="checkbox"/> From outside Denmark <input type="checkbox"/> From a commercial holding in Denmark <input type="checkbox"/> From a private breeder in Denmark <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Do not know
26	Is/was the companion/hobby pig(s) used for breeding?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Do not know
A	If pigs are/were used for breeding: What is/was the purpose of the breeding?	<input type="checkbox"/> For sale/rehoming <input type="checkbox"/> For meat production

¹ The definition of forest is based on FAO's (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations) definition (<https://openknowledge.fao.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/a6e225da-4a31-4e06-818d-ca3aeafd635/content>)

	Multiple answers can be selected.	<input type="checkbox"/> For own breeding purposes <input type="checkbox"/> To participate in competitions, exhibitions, shows, or other gatherings <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Do not know
B	<p>If pigs are/were used for breeding:</p> <p>Is/was the breeding carried out through natural mating or artificial insemination?</p> <p>Multiple answers can be selected.</p>	<input type="checkbox"/> Natural mating <input type="checkbox"/> Insemination with Danish semen <input type="checkbox"/> Insemination with semen from outside Denmark <input type="checkbox"/> Do not know

Living conditions and surroundings

27	Please describe the type of material the companion/hobby pig(s) lie/lay on. Multiple answers can be selected.	<input type="checkbox"/> Straw <input type="checkbox"/> Wood shavings <input type="checkbox"/> Basket <input type="checkbox"/> No bedding material is used <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify)
28	Do/did the companion/hobby pig(s) have access to outdoor areas on the premises, e.g. a paddock, pasture, or fenced garden?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, outdoor access e.g. in a paddock, pasture, or fenced garden <input type="checkbox"/> No
A	<p>If the pig(s) has/had outdoor access:</p> <p>How would you describe the fencing?</p> <p>Multiple answers can be selected.</p>	<input type="checkbox"/> Single fence <input type="checkbox"/> Double fence <input type="checkbox"/> Single electric fence <input type="checkbox"/> Double electric fence <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify)
29	Please select the category that best describes the area where the companion/hobby pig(s) live(s)	<input type="checkbox"/> In a city with more than 100,000 inhabitants <input type="checkbox"/> In a suburb with more than 100,000 inhabitants <input type="checkbox"/> In a city or an urban area with 10,000-100,000 inhabitants <input type="checkbox"/> In a city or an urban area with 5,000-9,999 inhabitants <input type="checkbox"/> In a city or an urban area with 2,000-4,999 inhabitants <input type="checkbox"/> In a city or an urban area with 1,000-1,999 inhabitants <input type="checkbox"/> In a city or an urban area with 500-999 inhabitants <input type="checkbox"/> In a city or an urban area with 200-499 inhabitants <input type="checkbox"/> In a city or an urban area with fewer than 200 inhabitants <input type="checkbox"/> In the countryside

Contact with other animals and people

30	<p>Do/did the companion/hobby pig(s) ever go outside the premises (e.g. for walks, visits, holidays, or other occasions)?</p> <p>Multiple answers can be selected.</p>	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, I walk/walked the pig(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, I take/took the pig(s) along when visiting others in Denmark, e.g. family, friends, acquaintances <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, I take/took the pig(s) along on trips within Denmark, e.g. to a summer house or holiday destinations <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, I take/took the pig(s) along on trips outside Denmark, e.g. on holiday <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify)
A	<p>If the owner walks/walked the pig(s):</p> <p>How many times per week do/did you or other members of the household/institution take the pig(s) outside the premises on walks?</p> <p>Please write your answer in numbers.</p>	[Numerical answer]
B	<p>If the owner takes/took the pig(s) on trips outside Denmark:</p> <p>How many times per year do/did you or other members of the household/institution take the pig(s) outside the premises?</p> <p>Please write your answer in numbers.</p>	[Numerical answer]
C	<p>If the owner takes/took the pig(s) on trips outside Denmark:</p> <p>Which countries have you visited with the pig(s)?</p>	[Text answer]
31	<p>Do/did you or other members of the household/institution ever participate in competitions, exhibitions, shows, or other gatherings with the companion/hobby pig(s)?</p> <p>Multiple answers can be selected.</p>	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, competitions, exhibitions, shows, or other gatherings within Denmark <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, competitions, exhibitions, shows, or other gatherings outside Denmark <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify)
A	<p>If the pig participates/participated in competitions, exhibitions, shows, or other gatherings within or outside Denmark:</p> <p>How many times per year do/did you participate in competitions, exhibitions, shows, or other gatherings with the companion/hobby pig(s)?</p> <p>Please write your answer in numbers.</p>	[Numerical answer]

32	Do/did you or other members of the household/institution ever go hunting in Denmark or outside Denmark? Multiple answers can be selected.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, within Denmark <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, outside Denmark <input type="checkbox"/> No
A	If anyone in the household/institution goes hunting within or outside Denmark: How many times per year do/did you or other members of the household/institution go hunting? Please write your answer in numbers.	[Numerical answer]
B	If anyone in the household/institution goes hunting within or outside Denmark: Do/did you or other members of the household/institution take any of the following precautions when returning home from hunting? Multiple answers can be selected.	<input type="checkbox"/> Shower <input type="checkbox"/> Washing clothes <input type="checkbox"/> Disinfecting clothes <input type="checkbox"/> Washing boots <input type="checkbox"/> Disinfecting boots <input type="checkbox"/> Washing weapons <input type="checkbox"/> Disinfecting weapons <input type="checkbox"/> Washing shooting stick/bipod <input type="checkbox"/> Disinfecting shooting stick/bipod <input type="checkbox"/> Avoiding contact with pigs on the same day as the hunt <input type="checkbox"/> Avoiding contact with pigs for 24 hours <input type="checkbox"/> Avoiding contact with pigs for 48 hours <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify)
33	How many times per year do/did a veterinarian visit the pig(s)? Please write your answer in numbers.	<input type="checkbox"/> [Numerical answer] <input type="checkbox"/> Only when needed

Feeding

34	What do/did the companion/hobby pig(s) eat, either as part of their daily feed or occasionally as a treat or reward? Multiple answers can be selected.	<input type="checkbox"/> Commercial feed (i.e. purchased feed) <input type="checkbox"/> Homemade feed <input type="checkbox"/> Leftovers from cooking, e.g. uncooked kitchen waste <input type="checkbox"/> Leftovers from cooking, e.g. cooked kitchen waste <input type="checkbox"/> Table scraps from own meals <input type="checkbox"/> Leftovers from restaurants or similar sources <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify)
A	If the pigs get/got homemade feed or leftovers/table scraps: How many times per week do/did the companion/hobby pig(s) receive meat leftovers?	[Numerical answer]

	Please write your answer in numbers.	
B	If the pigs get/got leftovers/table scraps: How many times per week do/did the companion/hobby pig(s) receive table scraps or other kitchen leftovers? Please write your answer in numbers.	[Numerical answer]

Slaughtering and disposal of deceased pigs and their waste

35	How are the pig(s)' faeces disposed of? Multiple answers can be selected.	<input type="checkbox"/> I throw it in household waste <input type="checkbox"/> I leave it in the paddock, pasture or garden <input type="checkbox"/> I use it as fertilizer in the garden or on fields <input type="checkbox"/> I store it in a manure tank or container <input type="checkbox"/> I compost it <input type="checkbox"/> It is collected/picked up by an external waste collection service <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify)
36	Are/were the companion/hobby pig(s) slaughtered for consumption? If so, how? Multiple answers can be selected.	<input type="checkbox"/> No, the pigs are/were not slaughtered for consumption/food production <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, they are/were sent for slaughter <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, I/we slaughter/slaughtered them myself/ourselves <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, a person outside the household comes/came to slaughter the pigs <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify)
A	If pigs are/were slaughtered: How many times per year are/were companion/hobby pigs slaughtered? Please write your answer in numbers.	[Numerical answer]
37	If a companion/hobby pig dies, how is/was the pig(s) disposed of? Multiple answers can be selected.	<input type="checkbox"/> Collected by DAKA <input type="checkbox"/> Sent for slaughter <input type="checkbox"/> Slaughtered at home <input type="checkbox"/> Buried, e.g. in the garden <input type="checkbox"/> I have not had any pigs that died <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify)

Knowledge of information materials

38	<p>Are you familiar with any of the following? Please select all answers that apply.</p>	<input type="checkbox"/> The Animal Protection Denmark's care guide for companion pigs <input type="checkbox"/> The Danish Veterinary and Food Administration's leaflet on keeping companion pigs <input type="checkbox"/> The Danish national PRRS reduction strategy <input type="checkbox"/> Information material about African Swine Fever <input type="checkbox"/> The swine influenza eradication program <input type="checkbox"/> No, I am not familiar with any of the above
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Comments

39	<p>If you have any comments about the questionnaire, please write them here.</p>	[Text answer]
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End of questionnaire

Thank you for your participation in the project! If you wish to receive a report about the study results, please send an e-mail to Helene Ane Jensen on e-mail: helene.jensen@sund.ku.dk